

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

Democratic Health Questionnaire (DHQ): *School Version*

Variable report & codebook related to the international
dataset [10.5281/zenodo.15341219](https://zenodo.org/record/15341219)

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Glossary

AE	Ars Electronica
ALTEREURO	European Alternatives
Critical ChangeLab	Democracy meets arts: Critical change labs for building democratic cultures through creative and narrative practices
DHQ	Democracy Health Questionnaire
ISRZ	Institute for Social Research in Zagreb
KERSNIKOVA	Kersnikova Institute
LATRA	LATRA
TCD	Trinity College Dublin
UB	University of Barcelona
UOULU	University of Oulu
WAAG	Waag Futurelab

1 Short description of Democratic Health Questionnaire (DHQ)

The Democracy Health Questionnaire (DHQ) was developed as part of the Horizon Europe Critical ChangeLab project to assess the democratic health of schools and institutions offering non-formal educational programs across ten partner countries.

Designed as a self-assessment tool, the DHQ enables schools and educational institutions to evaluate their current state of democratic health and plan future initiatives to enhance this vital aspect of their organization.

Two versions of the DHQ have been created: one for schools and another for institutions providing non-formal educational programmes. The questionnaire examines the democratic health of educational institutions by assessing the importance, current status, and five-year expectation regarding 26 democratic practices and four democratic values.

Ten language versions of school questionnaire are available at:

<https://zenodo.org/records/13767190>

2 Implementation of the Democracy Health Questionnaire (DHQ)

The DHQ was administered centrally using Alchemer, an online survey platform. As the task leader, ISRZ was responsible for setting up different versions of the DHQ, with each partner translating master version (English) into their national language.

All partners were responsible for distributing the questionnaire link to schools.

The following criteria guided the selection of schools for participation:

- Schools providing educational services to learners aged 11 to 18 (lower and upper secondary levels)
- Inclusion of public, private, and religious schools
- Ensuring geographic diversity, covering both urban and rural areas
- Inclusion of single-gender schools, where applicable.

The participants were heads of institutions or individuals responsible for educational programs.

3 Data collection start/end date

October 9th 2023 – March 9th 2024

4 Samples by country

Country	Partner	Questionnaire language version	Sample size
Austria	AE	German	90
Croatia	ISRZ	Croatian	196
Finland	UOULU	Finnish	92
France	ALTEREURO	French	33
Greece	LATRA	Greek	18
Ireland	TCD	English	87
Netherlands	WAAG	Dutch	170
Slovenia	KERSNIKOVA	Slovenian	59
Spain	UB	Spanish	16
Spain	UB	Catalan	73
TOTAL			834

5 Dataset preparation

Datasets for each language form of “DHQ – School” (10 versions) containing only complete cases were prepared.

Individual datasets were merged into an international dataset.

To ensure anonymisation, all variables related to participants' location and IP addresses were removed. Only anonymised data is made publicly available.

At the beginning of dataset, following four administrative variables were added:

- ID (unique school identifier),
- Type of DHQ questionnaire,
- Country code
- Language of DHQ.

During data preparation process, the dataset was checked for completeness, aberrant codes and consistency in response patterns (limited to the segment of background variables).

Missing data responses were coded as -1 across all variables. Only in exceptional cases aberrant responses were recoded as missing data.

No weighting has been applied to the dataset.

6 Variable report

6.1 Administrative variables

VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	ID
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	School ID
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	Numbers (1-n)
VARIABLE DESCRIPTION	Unique school identifier

VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	qtn_type
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Type of DHQ questionnaire
VARIABLE TYPE	Nominal
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 School 2 Educational institution providing non-formal programmes
VARIABLE DESCRIPTION	Identification of the DHQ version

VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	Country
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Country
VARIABLE TYPE	Nominal
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 Austria 2 Croatia 3 Finland 4 France 5 Greece 6 Ireland 7 Netherlands 8 Slovenia 9 Spain
VARIABLE DESCRIPTION	Country of questionnaire administration

VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	qnt_language
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Language of DHQ
VARIABLE TYPE	Nominal
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 German 2 Catalan 3 Croatian 4 Finnish 5 French 6 Greek 7 English 8 Dutch 9 Slovenian 10 Spanish
VARIABLE DESCRIPTION	Identification of language of DHQ

6.2 Background variables

ITEM NUMBER	Q1
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	education_target_group
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Provide education for students aged between 11 and 18
VARIABLE TYPE	Nominal
QUESTION FULL TEXT	We provide education for students aged between 11 and 18?
ANSWER CATEGORIES	<input type="radio"/> yes <input type="radio"/> no
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 yes 2 no

ITEM NUMBER	Q2
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	public_private
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Public vs. private school
VARIABLE TYPE	Nominal
QUESTION FULL TEXT	We are?
ANSWER CATEGORIES	<p>0 a public school - managed directly or indirectly by a public education authority, government agency, or governing board appointed by the government or elected by public franchise</p> <p>0 a private school - managed directly or indirectly by a non-government organisation, e.g. a church, trade union, business, or other private institution</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	<p>1 a public school - managed directly or indirectly by a public education authority, government agency</p> <p>2 a private school - managed directly or indirectly by a non-government organisation</p> <p>-1 N.A./missing</p>

ITEM NUMBER	Q3
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	location
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	School location
VARIABLE TYPE	Nominal
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Our school is located in...
ANSWER CATEGORIES	<input type="radio"/> a rural area, village, or settlement with fewer than 3,000 people <input type="radio"/> a small town (3,000 to 15,000 people) <input type="radio"/> a town (15,000 to 100,000 people) <input type="radio"/> a city (100,000 to 1,000,000 people) <input type="radio"/> a large city (with over 1,000,000 people)
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 a rural area, village, or settlement with fewer than 3,000 people 2 a small town (3,000 to 15,000 people) 3 a town (15,000 to 100,000 people) 4 a city (100,000 to 1,000,000 people) 5 a large city (with over 1,000,000 people) -1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q4
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	learners_number
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Total number of students aged 11 to 18 in the previous school year
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Please estimate the total number of students aged 11 to 18 in the previous school year.
ANSWER CATEGORIES	No categories
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q5
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	financing_education
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Free of charge vs. paid
VARIABLE TYPE	Nominal
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Education in our school is...?
ANSWER CATEGORIES	<input type="radio"/> free of charge <input type="radio"/> paid for by families <input type="radio"/> free of charge for some students and paid for by families for other students
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	1 free of charge 2 paid for by families 3 free of charge for some students and paid for by families for other students -1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q6
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	learners_percent_diff_language
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Percentage of students whose first language is different from the language of instruction
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Please estimate the percentage of students in your school whose first language is different from the language of instruction.
ANSWER CATEGORIES	No categories
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q7
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	learners_percent_ed_needs
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Percentage of students with additional educational needs
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Please estimate the percentage of students in your school with additional educational needs.
ANSWER CATEGORIES	No categories
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q8
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	learners_percent_dis_sococon
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Percentage of students from disadvantaged socioeconomic backgrounds
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Please estimate the percentage of students in your school from disadvantaged socioeconomic backgrounds.
ANSWER CATEGORIES	No categories
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q13
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development2_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	The school's educational programme is developed through open discussion and exchange of views between staff members. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.2. The school's educational programme is developed through open discussion and exchange of views between staff members. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q14
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development2_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	The school's educational programme is developed through open discussion and exchange of views between staff members. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.2. The school's educational programme is developed through open discussion and exchange of views between staff members. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="margin-right: 20px;">Not at all (0%)</div> <div style="flex-grow: 1; position: relative;"> <div style="position: absolute; left: 50%; transform: translate(-50%, 0);">Somewhat (50%)</div> <div style="position: absolute; right: 20px;">Very much (100%)</div> </div> <div style="margin-left: 20px;">100</div> </div>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q15
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development3_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	The school’s educational programme is developed to address the needs of diverse groups within the wider community. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.3. The school’s educational programme is developed to address the needs of diverse groups within the wider community. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q16
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development3_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	The school's educational programme is developed to address the needs of diverse groups within the wider community. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.3. The school's educational programme is developed to address the needs of diverse groups within the wider community. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q17
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development3_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	The school's educational programme is developed to address the needs of diverse groups within the wider community. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.3. The school's educational programme is developed to address the needs of diverse groups within the wider community. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q18
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development4_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Responsibility for the natural and social environment is taken into account in the development of the school's educational programme. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.4. Responsibility for the natural and social environment is taken into account in the development of the school's educational programme. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q19
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development4_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Responsibility for the natural and social environment is taken into account in the development of the school's educational programme. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.4. Responsibility for the natural and social environment is taken into account in the development of the school's educational programme. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q20
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development4_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Responsibility for the natural and social environment is taken into account in the development of the school's educational programme. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.4. Responsibility for the natural and social environment is taken into account in the development of the school's educational programme. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q21
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development5_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	A variety of approaches and/or viewpoints are considered in the development of the school's educational program. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.5. A variety of approaches and/or viewpoints are considered in the development of the school's educational program. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%) </div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="width: 100px; margin-right: 20px;">0</div> <div style="width: 100px; margin-right: 20px;">10</div> <div style="width: 100px; margin-right: 20px;">20</div> <div style="width: 100px; margin-right: 20px;">30</div> <div style="width: 100px; margin-right: 20px;">40</div> <div style="width: 100px; margin-right: 20px;">50</div> <div style="width: 100px; margin-right: 20px;">60</div> <div style="width: 100px; margin-right: 20px;">70</div> <div style="width: 100px; margin-right: 20px;">80</div> <div style="width: 100px; margin-right: 20px;">90</div> <div style="width: 100px;">100</div> </div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-top: 5px;"> <input type="range" value="0"/> </div>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q22
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development5_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	A variety of approaches and/or viewpoints are considered in the development of the school's educational program. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.5. A variety of approaches and/or viewpoints are considered in the development of the school's educational program. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q23
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development5_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	A variety of approaches and/or viewpoints are considered in the development of the school's educational program. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.5. A variety of approaches and/or viewpoints are considered in the development of the school's educational program. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q24
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development6_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Decisions about the school's educational programme are collaborative. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	A.6. Decisions about the school's educational programme are collaborative. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q26
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	development6_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Decisions about the school's educational programme are collaborative. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>A.6. Decisions about the school's educational programme are collaborative. EXPECTATION</p> <p><i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q27
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	access1_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds have equal opportunities to access the school's educational services. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	B.1. Individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds have equal opportunities to access the school's educational services. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q28
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	accessl_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds have equal opportunities to access the school's educational services. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	B.1. Individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds have equal opportunities to access the school's educational services. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q29
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	accessl_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds have equal opportunities to access the school's educational services. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>B.1. Individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds have equal opportunities to access the school's educational services. EXPECTATION</p> <p><i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q31
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	access2_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Ensuring access for students from diverse groups within the community is embedded in institutional policies and procedures. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	B.2. Ensuring access for students from diverse groups within the community is embedded in institutional policies and procedures. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q32
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	access2_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Ensuring access for students from diverse groups within the community is embedded in institutional policies and procedures. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	B.2. Ensuring access for students from diverse groups within the community is embedded in institutional policies and procedures. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q33
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	access3_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Information about the school's educational programme and access criteria is easily accessible to all community members. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	B.3. Information about the school's educational programme and access criteria is easily accessible to all community members. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q34
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	access3_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Information about the school's educational programme and access criteria is easily accessible to all community members. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	B.3. Information about the school's educational programme and access criteria is easily accessible to all community members. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q35
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	access3_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Information about the school's educational programme and access criteria is easily accessible to all community members. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>B.3. Information about the school's educational programme and access criteria is easily accessible to all community members. EXPECTATION</p> <p><i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p> <p></p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q36
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery1_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Students have the opportunity to influence the content of teaching and learning. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.1. Students have the opportunity to influence the content of teaching and learning. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q38																											
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery1_expectation																											
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Students have the opportunity to influence the content of teaching and learning. - EXPECTATION																											
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale																											
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.1. Students have the opportunity to influence the content of teaching and learning. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>																											
SCALE	<table border="0" style="width: 100%; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td>Not at all (0%)</td> <td></td> <td>Somewhat (50%)</td> <td></td> <td>Very much (100%)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>10</td> <td>20</td> <td>30</td> <td>40</td> <td>50</td> <td>60</td> <td>70</td> <td>80</td> <td>90</td> <td>100</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="11"> </td> </tr> </table>	Not at all (0%)		Somewhat (50%)		Very much (100%)	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100											
Not at all (0%)		Somewhat (50%)		Very much (100%)																								
0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100																		
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing																											

ITEM NUMBER	Q39
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery2_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Students have the opportunity to influence the choice of teaching and learning methods. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.2. Students have the opportunity to influence the choice of teaching and learning methods. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q40
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery2_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Students have the opportunity to influence the choice of teaching and learning methods. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.2. Students have the opportunity to influence the choice of teaching and learning methods. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p> <p></p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q41
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery2_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Students have the opportunity to influence the choice of teaching and learning methods. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.2. Students have the opportunity to influence the choice of teaching and learning methods. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q42
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery3_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Teaching and learning are grounded in methods that encourage students' active participation. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.3. Teaching and learning are grounded in methods that encourage students' active participation. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q43
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery3_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Teaching and learning are grounded in methods that encourage students' active participation. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.3. Teaching and learning are grounded in methods that encourage students' active participation. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q44
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery3_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Teaching and learning are grounded in methods that encourage students' active participation. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.3. Teaching and learning are grounded in methods that encourage students' active participation. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q46
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery4_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	The teaching and learning environment encourages open discussion and the expression of diverse opinions. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.4. The teaching and learning environment encourages open discussion and the expression of diverse opinions. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p> <p></p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q47
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery4_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	The teaching and learning environment encourages open discussion and the expression of diverse opinions. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.4. The teaching and learning environment encourages open discussion and the expression of diverse opinions. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q48
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery5_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Individualised support is provided for students with additional educational needs. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.5. Individualised support is provided for students with additional educational needs. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%) </div> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; margin-top: 5px;"> 0102030405060708090100 </div>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q49
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery5_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Individualised support is provided for students with additional educational needs. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>C.5. Individualised support is provided for students with additional educational needs.</p> <p>CURRENT STATE</p> <p><i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q50
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery5_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Individualised support is provided for students with additional educational needs. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.5. Individualised support is provided for students with additional educational needs. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%) </div>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q51
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery6_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Students are introduced to and are encouraged to respect the diversities within their teaching and learning group(s). - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.6. Students are introduced to and are encouraged to respect the diversities within their teaching and learning group(s). IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; align-items: flex-start;"> <div style="text-align: center;">Not at all (0%)</div> <div style="text-align: center;">Somewhat (50%)</div> <div style="text-align: center;">Very much (100%)</div> </div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center; margin-top: 5px;"> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">0</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">10</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">20</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">30</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">40</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">50</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">60</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">70</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">80</div> <div style="text-align: center; margin-right: 10px;">90</div> <div style="text-align: center;">100</div> </div> <div style="margin-top: 5px;"> </div>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q52
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery6_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Students are introduced to and are encouraged to respect the diversities within their teaching and learning group(s). – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.6. Students are introduced to and are encouraged to respect the diversities within their teaching and learning group(s). CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q53
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery6_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Students are introduced to and are encouraged to respect the diversities within their teaching and learning group(s). - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.6. Students are introduced to and are encouraged to respect the diversities within their teaching and learning group(s). EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q54
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery7_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	All students, regardless of their attributes, have an equal opportunity to complete their education. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.7. All students, regardless of their attributes, have an equal opportunity to complete their education. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q55
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery7_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	All students, regardless of their attributes, have an equal opportunity to complete their education. – CURRENT STATUS
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.7. All students, regardless of their attributes, have an equal opportunity to complete their education. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q58
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery8_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Students' rights and responsibilities are clearly defined and communicated. – CURRENT STATUS
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.8. Students' rights and responsibilities are clearly defined and communicated. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q59
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery8_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Students' rights and responsibilities are clearly defined and communicated. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.8. Students' rights and responsibilities are clearly defined and communicated. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>A horizontal scale ranging from 0 to 100. The scale is marked with tick marks at intervals of 10. Labels are placed above the scale: "Not at all (0%)", "Somewhat (50%)", and "Very much (100%)". A grey circle is positioned at the 0 mark.</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q60
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery9_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Clearly defined procedures exist in the case of a potential violation of either students' or teachers' rights. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.9. Clearly defined procedures exist in the case of a potential violation of either students' or teachers' rights. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="margin-right: 20px;">Not at all (0%)</div> <div style="margin-right: 20px;">Somewhat (50%)</div> <div>Very much (100%)</div> </div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="margin-right: 5px;">0</div> <div style="margin-right: 10px;">10</div> <div style="margin-right: 10px;">20</div> <div style="margin-right: 10px;">30</div> <div style="margin-right: 10px;">40</div> <div style="margin-right: 10px;">50</div> <div style="margin-right: 10px;">60</div> <div style="margin-right: 10px;">70</div> <div style="margin-right: 10px;">80</div> <div style="margin-right: 10px;">90</div> <div style="margin-right: 10px;">100</div> </div>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q61
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery9_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Clearly defined procedures exist in the case of a potential violation of either students' or teachers' rights. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.9. Clearly defined procedures exist in the case of a potential violation of either students' or teachers' rights. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%) </div> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> 0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100 </div>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q62
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery9_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Clearly defined procedures exist in the case of a potential violation of either students' or teachers' rights. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.9. Clearly defined procedures exist in the case of a potential violation of either students' or teachers' rights. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q63
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery10_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Conflicts that arise during teaching and learning are resolved in a constructive and inclusive manner. – IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.10. Conflicts that arise during teaching and learning are resolved in a constructive and inclusive manner. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q64
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery10_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Conflicts that arise during teaching and learning are resolved in a constructive and inclusive manner. – CURRENT STATUS
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.10. Conflicts that arise during teaching and learning are resolved in a constructive and inclusive manner. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q66
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery11_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Teaching and learning incorporate responsibility for the natural and social environment. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.11. Teaching and learning incorporate responsibility for the natural and social environment. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q68
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	delivery11_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Teaching and learning incorporate responsibility for the natural and social environment. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	C.11. Teaching and learning incorporate responsibility for the natural and social environment. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q69
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpactl_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Students' evaluations and feedback are used to improve the school's educational programme. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.1. Students' evaluations and feedback are used to improve the school's educational programme. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q70
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpactl_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Students' evaluations and feedback are used to improve the school's educational programme. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.1. Students' evaluations and feedback are used to improve the school's educational programme. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q72
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact2_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Outcomes of the school's educational programme are shared and discussed with the wider community. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.2. Outcomes of the school's educational programme are shared and discussed with the wider community. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p> <p></p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q73
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact2_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Outcomes of the school's educational programme are shared and discussed with the wider community. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.2. Outcomes of the school's educational programme are shared and discussed with the wider community. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p> <p><input type="range"/></p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q74
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact2_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Outcomes of the school's educational programme are shared and discussed with the wider community. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.2. Outcomes of the school's educational programme are shared and discussed with the wider community. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q75
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact3_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Students develop competencies for active citizenship through the school's educational programme. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.3. Students develop competencies for active citizenship through the school's educational programme. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%) </div> <div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="text-align: center;">0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</div> </div>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q76
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact3_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Students develop competencies for active citizenship through the school's educational programme. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.3. Students develop competencies for active citizenship through the school's educational programme. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q77
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact3_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Students develop competencies for active citizenship through the school's educational programme. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.3. Students develop competencies for active citizenship through the school's educational programme. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q78
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact4_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Evaluation of the school's educational programme considers multiple indicators. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.4. Evaluation of the school's educational programme considers multiple indicators. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q82
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact5_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	The impact of the school's educational programme on the wider community is evaluated. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.5. The impact of the school's educational programme on the wider community is evaluated. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q84
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact6_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Sources of funding are publicly disclosed. - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.6. Sources of funding are publicly disclosed. IMPORTANCE <i>How important do you consider this practice?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q85
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact6_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Sources of funding are publicly disclosed. – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.6. Sources of funding are publicly disclosed. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this practice currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q86
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	outcomesimpact6_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Sources of funding are publicly disclosed. - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	D.6. Sources of funding are publicly disclosed. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this practice will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

6.4 Main variables – democratic values

ITEM NUMBER	Q87
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	participation_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participation - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>Participation refers to the active involvement of students, staff, and other stakeholders in the programme development, learning process, and overall functioning of the institution. It goes beyond mere attendance and encompasses engagement, interaction, collaboration, and contribution within the educational community.</p> <p>IMPORTANCE</p> <p><i>How important do you consider this value?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q88
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	participation_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participation – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>Participation refers to the active involvement of students, staff, and other stakeholders in the programme development, learning process, and overall functioning of the institution. It goes beyond mere attendance and encompasses engagement, interaction, collaboration, and contribution within the educational community.</p> <p>CURRENT STATE</p> <p><i>To what extent is this value currently present in your school?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q89
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	participation_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Participation - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>Participation refers to the active involvement of students, staff, and other stakeholders in the programme development, learning process, and overall functioning of the institution. It goes beyond mere attendance and encompasses engagement, interaction, collaboration, and contribution within the educational community.</p> <p>EXPECTATION</p> <p><i>To what extent do you expect this value will be present in your school in 5 years?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q91
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	acctrans_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Accountability and transparency – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>Accountability and transparency ensures that the institution is responsible for its actions, decisions, and outcomes while maintaining an open and honest relationship with its internal and external stakeholders. It fosters openness and accessibility of information related to the functioning, decision-making processes, and performance of an educational institution.</p> <p>CURRENT STATE</p> <p><i>To what extent is this value currently present in your school?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q92
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	acctrans_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Accountability and transparency - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>Accountability and transparency ensures that the institution is responsible for its actions, decisions, and outcomes while maintaining an open and honest relationship with its internal and external stakeholders. It fosters openness and accessibility of information related to the functioning, decision-making processes, and performance of an educational institution.</p> <p>EXPECTATION</p> <p><i>To what extent do you expect this value will be present in your school in 5 years?</i></p>
SCALE	<div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <div style="margin-right: 20px;">Not at all (0%)</div> <div style="margin-right: 20px;">Somewhat (50%)</div> <div style="margin-right: 20px;">Very much (100%)</div> </div>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q93
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	EDI_importance
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Equality, diversity, and inclusion - IMPORTANCE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>Equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) presumes institutional dedication towards equal representation and opportunities, as well as respect and justice for students from various backgrounds, such as ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, and abilities. Institutions that value EDI foster a sense of belonging, seek diverse perspectives, and encourage engagement to maximise the potential of every individual.</p> <p>IMPORTANCE</p> <p><i>How important do you consider this value?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q94
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	EDI_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Equality, diversity, and inclusion – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>Equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) presumes institutional dedication towards equal representation and opportunities, as well as respect and justice for students from various backgrounds, such as ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, and abilities. Institutions that value EDI foster a sense of belonging, seek diverse perspectives, and encourage engagement to maximise the potential of every individual.</p> <p>CURRENT STATE</p> <p><i>To what extent is this value currently present in your school?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q95
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	EDI_expectation
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Equality, diversity, and inclusion - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) presumes institutional dedication towards equal representation and opportunities, as well as respect and justice for students from various backgrounds, such as ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, and abilities. Institutions that value EDI foster a sense of belonging, seek diverse perspectives, and encourage engagement to maximise the potential of every individual. EXPECTATION <i>To what extent do you expect this value will be present in your school in 5 years?</i>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q97
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	ecosocresp_currentstate
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Eco-social responsibility – CURRENT STATE
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	Eco-social responsibility refers to the ethical obligation and accountability the institution has towards the environment and society, recognising their interconnectedness and advocating for sustainable practices that minimise harm to both. Eco-social responsibility encourages actions that prioritise environmental conservation, social justice, and the wellbeing of the wider community, aiming for a more equitable and sustainable future. CURRENT STATE <i>To what extent is this value currently present in your school?</i>
SCALE	
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

ITEM NUMBER	Q98
VARIABLE NAME IN THE DATA SET	ecosocresp_expectation - EXPECTATION
VARIABLE LABEL IN THE DATA SET	Eco-social responsibility
VARIABLE TYPE	Scale
QUESTION FULL TEXT	<p>Eco-social responsibility refers to the ethical obligation and accountability the institution has towards the environment and society, recognising their interconnectedness and advocating for sustainable practices that minimise harm to both. Eco-social responsibility encourages actions that prioritise environmental conservation, social justice, and the wellbeing of the wider community, aiming for a more equitable and sustainable future.</p> <p>EXPECTATION</p> <p><i>To what extent do you expect this value will be present in your school in 5 years?</i></p>
SCALE	<p>Not at all (0%) Somewhat (50%) Very much (100%)</p> <p>0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100</p>
VARIABLE CODE LIST IN THE DATA SET	-1 N.A./missing

